

A novel deep learning model-based Alzheimer's disease diagnosis system using MRI image

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Abstract: Alzheimer's disease (AD) is an irreversible, progressive brain disorder that slowly destroys memory and thinking skills. It is one of the leading types of dementia. In order to achieve an accurate and timely diagnosis, and for the detection of AD in its early stages, numerous Artificial Intelligence (AI) based Computer-aided Diagnostic (CAD) approaches have been proposed using data from brain imaging. But the existing research works have a lot of problems, in order to solve those research problems, this research methodology proposed a novel deep learning model-based AD diagnosis approach. This research methodology has pre-processing, segmentation, landmark detection, feature extraction, feature selection, and classification phases. In the pre-processing stage, the input image is improved by filtering, contrast enhancement, normalization, etc. Then, the brain tissues are segmented from the pre-processed image and the landmark is also detected from the same pre-processed image. From the segmented tissue, the global and local features are extracted. Then, important features are selected, and the selected features, the obtained high-level statistical spatial features, and longitudinal features from the detected landmarks are given as input to the novel deep learning model for diagnosis of the AD. In experimental analysis, the performance of the proposed research methodology is analyzed with the existing research methodology based on performance metrics.

Key words: *Alzheimer's Disease (AD), Segmentation, Land-mark detection, high-level statistical spatial features, longitudinal features, global features, local features, and novel deep learning model.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease is a common cause of dementia, which is a progressive brain disorder that can cause brain cell damage and a patient affected with this disease can decline in their behavior, thinking, and social activities skills (Salehi et al., 2020). The problems usually grow slowly and become severe enough to interact with everyday life. Although elderliness is the major risk factor, AD is an old-age illness. In its early stages, memory loss is minimal, while the communication

and capacity of the patient to respond significantly degrade during the initial stages (Guo & Zhang, 2020). In severe cases, patients might even fail to recognize their family members. According to reports from the World Health Organization (WHO), Alzheimer's disease is the sixth leading cause of death in the world (Dua et al., 2020). There are approximately 50 million people all around the world who have Alzheimer's disease and different types of dementia. The total number of new cases of dementia each year worldwide is nearly 10 million, implying 1 new case every 3 seconds. The number of people with dementia is expected to increase to 82 million in 2030 and 152 million in 2050 (Hussain et al., 2020). Over the last few decades, considerable progress has been made towards a greater understanding of the biological

mechanisms implicated in the generation of the disease, which has made it possible to know that the pathological brain changes begin up to 15-20 years before the onset of symptoms, a period termed “preclinical AD” (Bringas et al., 2020). Alzheimer reports two common abnormalities in the brain of this patient, “1. Dense layers of protein deposited outside and between the nerve cells. 2. Areas of damaged nerve fibers inside the nerve cells instead of being directly had become tangled” (Janghel & Rathore, 2021). So the diagnosis of Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is severely needed. Diagnosis is a major task in the medical treatment of any health problems. With the rapid developments of the neuroimaging techniques, it is getting possible to diagnose AD by using the neuro-images like some other disorders at the brain activity. This is due to the fact that these images hold a high relationship with the brain topology and they show the alterations in the brain morphology. In the Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images, the regions with the cells affected by the degeneration of the disease take very low-intensity values, so they appear darker with respect to healthy parts (Puente-Castro et al., 2020). Hence, clinical research and research studies mainly use MRI images for the diagnosis of AD. Because, diagnosis of the disease at the early stages can give a chance to control and slow down the results of it (Uysal & Ozturk, 2020). Artificial Intelligence in the medical field can play an important role for lab technicians by accurately identifying the diseased part in the blood stool and urine, as well as skin tissues. If there is any suspected abnormality in blood, urine, or tissues, our machine-learning model can detect it automatically. This is the main advantage of Artificial intelligence (Ahmad & Pothuganti, 2020). Recently, in the same way, AD has also been diagnosed by many researchers. The ML models that have been employed in this context

are: (1) classic models - Random Forest, Bayesian Network, Decision trees, K-Nearest Neighbours, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines, and Linear discriminant analysis, (2) deep learning models - Convolutional neural networks (CNN), Recurrent neural networks (RNN) and custom architectures, (3) Bayesian ML models (Lopez-Martin et al., 2020). The classic models require complex preprocessing to get hand-craft features for classification (Xia et al., 2020). The deep learning models can automatically build a more abstract high-level representation of the learning system by integrating low-level features embedded in the data (Pan et al., 2020). But, the deep learning model also has some challenges; so to solve that problem, this research proposed a novel method for AD diagnosis.

2. RELATED WORK

(Fan et al., 2020) presented a support vector machine (SVM) model method to classify and predict different disease processes of Alzheimer's disease based on structural brain magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) imaging data, so as to help the auxiliary diagnosis of the disease. In the research, the extracted MRI data and the SVM model were combined to obtain more accurate classification prediction results. The accuracy of classification and prediction was the best. According to the predicted results, the data characteristics related to diseases were determined, which provided a basis for clinical and basic research, etiology, and pathological changes.

(Bi et al., 2020) focused on the problem of functional brain network classification for Alzheimer's disease detection. The research explores two types of deep features, i.e., regional connectivity positional features and adjacency positional features. Convolutional and recurrent learning methods were implemented to learn the

deep features of the brain network directly without manual feature extraction. Furthermore, Extreme Learning Machine (ELM)-boosting structure was also implemented to further improve the performance. The evaluation and comparison results indicate satisfactory learning ability for the applications.

(Nawaz et al., 2021) developed an Alzheimer's stage detection system based on deep features using a pre-trained AlexNet model, by transferring the initial layers from the pre-trained AlexNet model and extracting the deep features from the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). For the classification of extracted deep features, the researchers used the widely used machine learning algorithms including Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), and Random Forest (RF). The evaluation results of the scheme show that a deep feature-based model outperformed the handcrafted and deep learning method with better accuracy. The model also outperforms existing state-of-the-art methods.

(Liu et al., 2021) suggested a deep separable convolutional neural network model for Alzheimer's Disease (AD) classification. The Depth-wise Separable Convolution (DSC) was used to replace the conventional convolution. Compared to the traditional neural networks, the parameters and computing cost of the neural network were found greatly reduced. The parameters and computational costs of the neural network were found to be significantly reduced compared with conventional neural networks. With its low power consumption, the model was particularly suitable to embed mobile devices. Experimental findings show that the DSC algorithm, based on the OASIS magnetic resonance imaging dataset, was very successful in AD detection. Moreover, transfer learning was

employed in the work to improve model performance.

(Murugan et al., 2021) presented a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture to perform AD classification. By considering four stages of dementia and conducting a particular diagnosis, the model generates high-resolution disease probability maps from the local brain structure to a multilayer perceptron and provides accurate, intuitive visualizations of individual Alzheimer's disease risk. To avoid the problem of class imbalance, the samples were evenly distributed among the classes. The obtained MRI image dataset from Kaggle had a major class imbalance problem. A DEMentia NETwork (DEMNET) was suggested to detect the dementia stages from MRI. The experimental results show that the approach attains better performance than the existing research methodologies.

(Tufail et al., 2020) intended to construct multiple deep 2D Convolutional Neural Networks (2D-CNNs) to learn various features from local brain images, which were combined to make the final classification for AD diagnosis. The whole brain image was passed through two transfer learning architectures; Inception version 3 and Xception, as well as a custom Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), built with the help of separable convolutional layers, which automatically learned the generic features from imaging data for classification. The study was conducted using cross-sectional T1-weighted structural MRI brain images from the Open Access Series of Imaging Studies (OASIS) database to maintain the size and contrast over different MRI scans. Experimental results show that the transfer learning approaches exceed the performance of non-transfer learning-based approaches demonstrating the effectiveness

of these approaches for the binary AD classification task.

(Farheen et al., 2019) conducted to explore the effectiveness of resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging and advanced deep learning techniques to perform multi-class classification and diagnosis of AD and its progressive stages. The study presented deep residual neural networks combined with a transfer learning approach for performing the classification of 6 AD stages. It incorporates different weight initialization schemes and network architectures to evaluate the dataset. The Analysis of results indicates that the classification and prediction of neurodegenerative brain disorders such as AD using functional magnetic resonance imaging and advanced deep learning methods was promising for clinical decision-making and have the potential to assist in the early diagnosis of AD and its associated stages.

(Mehmood et al., 2020) developed a Siamese Convolutional Neural Network (SCNN) model inspired by VGG-16 (also called Oxford Net) to classify dementia stages. In the approach, the research extends the insufficient and imbalanced data by using augmentation approaches. Experiments were performed on a publicly available dataset open access series of imaging studies (OASIS), by using the proposed approach, excellent test accuracy was achieved for the classification of dementia stages. The research compared the model with the state-of-the-art models and discovered that the model outperformed the state-of-the-art models in terms of performance, efficiency, and accuracy.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Existing research works have some drawbacks which are described as follows,

- For the diagnosis of AD, the clinical history was also used and by knowing if the person has some genetic disorder. Sometimes it is also possible that the doctor may not be able to detect the disease.
- The performance of the approach (Bi et al., 2020) was still vulnerable to different Region of Interest (ROI) positions in the functional brain network.
- The existing (Murugan et al., 2021) approach was tested with the less number of data so it was not efficient and had the higher computational complexity problem.
- The approach (Tufail et al., 2020) had the class imbalance and data leakage problems and found that they tend towards increasing the classification performance bias.
- Existing research studies only considers the specific category of people.
- In conventional approach the feature was extracted from the single part of the image not considers all the tissues of the input MRI.
- Also the existing research works considers only local feature (or) global features not considers the both features.
- The state-of-the-art deep learning models are optimized to work with natural (every day) images. These models also require a lot of balanced training data to prevent overfitting in the network.
- Very high dimensional features make an overfitting problem.
- Noisy Features was adversely affect the learning performance of the subsequent classification model.

- Existing studies only extracted the features from the segmented tissues which wasn't enough for train the data.

4. CHALLENGES IN AND DIAGNOSIS

The AD diagnosis using MRI imaging approach had some challenges which are enlisted here:

- Developing an automated Alzheimer's Disease detection and classification model is a pretty challenging task.
- The vast amount of data from various modalities, such as genetics, proteomics, transcriptomic and imaging, and clinical features, impose great challenges in data integration and analysis.
- In clinical testing, Alzheimer's trials tend to be slower to enrol participants, take longer to complete, and are more expensive than trials in most other therapeutic categories.
- One of the initial challenges was the significance class imbalance problem.
- Finding a computational approach for the early detection of AD patients who do not exhibit any clinical signs of AD at the time of the test is an open challenge.
- Voxel-based approaches exploit the voxel intensities as the classification feature. The interpretation of the results is simple and intuitive in voxel-based representations, but they suffer from the overfitting problem since there are limited (e.g., tens or hundreds) in subjects with very high (millions)-dimensional features, which is a major challenge for AD diagnosis based on neuroimaging.
- More analytical methods are needed to provide rigorous data integration and analysis. A general data integration method usually requires extensive feature selection from each platform to reduce the computational burden in the data integrating step.

5. MOTIVATION

The motivation for the creation of innovation to support the battle against Alzheimer's disease is evident, not only from an ethical perspective but also due to the continuous proliferation of Alzheimer's cases in our society. Today, 50 million people worldwide live with dementia, and two-thirds of them have Alzheimer's disease. Alzheimer's cases have overtaken cancer to become the most feared disease in the United States, with a new case appearing every three seconds in the world. At the moment, the diagnosis of this disease is made by combining an analysis of the patient's medical history, different cognitive tests, and various clinical tests, such as photographic scans of the brain. But, all these tests are not enough for an early diagnosis of AD. Mainly, the patient's medical history was not enough because it's not the disease of age, it's the disease of the brain and patients may show Symptoms like loss of memory, difficulty in finding the right words or understanding what people are saying, difficulty in performing previously routine tasks and personality and mood changes. In this situation, smart diagnostic systems provide safe clinical support to clinicians. So, this research considers the novel deep learning model-based AD diagnosis system.

6. OBJECTIVES

The proposed research methodology has many objectives. Thus, the objectives are given as follows,

- To applied the different process for remove unwanted things in image for further phase.
- To considers the both tissue based features and the landmark based features.

- To present the efficient segmentation approach for segment the brain tissues such as GM, WM, CSF, etc.
- To extract both the global and local features from the segmented brain tissues.
- To extract both the high-level statistical spatial features and longitudinal features.
- To reduce the computation time and error the important features are only selected.
- To diagnosis the AD the novel deep learning mode is presented.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Alzheimer's disease is an incurable, progressive neurological brain disorder. Earlier detection of Alzheimer's disease can help with proper treatment and prevent brain tissue damage. Several statistical and machine learning models have been exploited by researchers for Alzheimer's disease diagnosis. Analyzing magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a common practice for Alzheimer's disease diagnosis in clinical research. Detection of Alzheimer's disease is exacting due to the similarity in Alzheimer's disease MRI data and standard healthy MRI data of older people. Recently, advanced deep learning techniques have successfully demonstrated human-level performance in numerous fields including medical image analysis. But those approach based AD diagnosis still have many challenges which is enlisted in the problem statement section. To solve that problem this research methodology proposed a novel deep learning approach based AD diagnosis system. The proposed research methodology consists of six phases namely, pre-processing, segmentation, landmark detection, feature extraction, feature selection and classification.

Initially, the input MRI image is pre-processed to reduce the unwanted things in the input image for reduce the error during the diagnosis stage. The

image is pre-processed by different procedures such as, brain extraction, motion correction, intensity normalization, filtering, conversion, and contrast enhancement. For this process the novel and efficient methods are carried out. After that from the pre-processed image the tissues of the brain tumor such as White Matter (WM), Gray Matter (GM), Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF), etc are segmented by using the efficient segmentation approaches. Also, from the pre-processed image the landmark is detected by landmark mark detection algorithm for extracting the high-level statistical spatial features and longitudinal features for obtain more information from the input image. From the segmented brain tissues also the global, and local features such as, transform, shape, texture, geometry, etc are extracted. From the extracted features to reduce the overfitting problem and computational time of the classifier this research methodology considers the feature selection algorithms, such as heuristic algorithms and the dimensionality reduction algorithms. Then, the selected features and the extracted landmark features are given as input to the novel deep learning classifier. Thus, the classifier diagnosis the AD and Non-AD images. Deep neural networks have training time problem and error problem. This problem was raised by the reason of choosing an inappropriate activation function, not scaling the data, overfitting problem, and weight initialization. To solve those problem this research methodology proposed a novel deep learning model for AD diagnosis system. Finally, in performance analysis the proposed methodology is analyzed with the existing research methodologies based on accuracy, precision, recall, F-measure, specificity, sensitivity, error rate, computational time, Mathew's Correlation Coefficient (MCC), etc. The block diagram for the proposed research is shown in Figure 1,

Figure 1: Block diagram for the proposed research work

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

8.1 Database Description

For the performance analysis this research methodology is evaluated using the different benchmark of the dataset such as Alzheimer ‘s Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI) from <https://adni.loni.usc.edu/>, Australian Imaging, Biomarkers and Lifestyle (AIBL) from <https://aibl.csiro.au/>, Open Access Series of Imaging Studies (OASIS) from <https://www.oasis-brains.org/>, and Minimal Interval Resonance Imaging in Alzheimer’s Disease (MIRIAD) from <https://bmi.ana.med.uni-muenchen.de/miriad/downloads> .

8.2 Software Requirement

The proposed work is implemented in the working platform of PYTHON. Python is a widely-used general-purpose, high-level programming language. It was mainly developed to emphasize code readability, and its syntax allows programmers to express concepts in fewer lines of code. Python is a programming language that lets you work quickly and integrate systems more

efficiently. The virtual environment tool creates an isolated python environment (in the form of a directory) that is completely separated from the system-wide Python environment.

8.3 Hardware Requirements

The hardware requirements are specified as follows,

Processor: Intel i5/core i7

CPU Speed: 3.20 GHz

OS: Windows 10

System Type: 64 bit

RAM: 4GB

For the classification purpose the random forest classifier is used. The random forest classifier reduces the overfitting & underfitting problem and performs classification tasks with higher accuracy. The output of the random forest model is given in terms of confusion matrix and a graph which shows the output of the random forest classifier. It shows that random forest classifier produces accurate results when compared to other classifiers.

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